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Influence Of The Utilization Of Quickbook On The Effective Teaching Of Accounting Courses In Business Education In Tertiary Institutions In Cross River State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of the utilization of QuickBook on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The main purpose of the study is to determine the influence of utilization of accounting software on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education. It has one specific purpose, one research questions and one hypotheses to guide the study. The researcher used survey research design; the population for the study is 106 academic staff of the institutions in Cross River State that teach Business Education. There was no sampling. The researcher used census population as the entire population was manageable. The geographical area of the study is Cross River State while the content area of the study is the influence of the utilization of accounting software on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education. A structures questionnaire with four point rating scale was used for data collection. The data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation while statistical t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that utilization of accounting software has positive influence on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education. Educational implications of the findings include organising workshop and seminar for lecturers, the need to publish text books in accounting among others. The researcher recommended that the use of accounting software should be encouraged to be used in the teaching of accounting courses in Business Education. It should be included in the curriculum of accounting programmes. It was suggested that further study should be carried out on the influence of gender on the utilization of accounting software in the teaching of accounting courses.

Keywords: Accounting software, QuickBook teaching, accounting courses, Business education

INTRODUCTION

Business Education is a vocational programme designed to equip the recipients with requisite skills needed for general employment; as a teacher, office and business manager or as an entrepreneur. The primary goal of Business Education is to produce skilful and dynamic business teachers, office administrators and business men and women that will be effectively competent in the job market (Gadzama and Olorunmowaju, 2024) In the assertion of Okoli in Okoro (2013), Business Education is that aspect of the total educational programme that provides the knowledge, skills, understanding and attitudes needed to perform effectively in the business world as a producer and/or consumer of goods

and services that business offers. According to Abumchukwu, in Gadzama and Olorunmwaju (2024), Business Education is an aspect of total educational programme which provides the recipients with knowledge, skills, understanding and attitude. According to Odike and Nnaekwe (2019), Business Education is a program of study and an aspect of vocational education programme offered in both secondary and tertiary institutions of learning in Nigeria. The common factor in all the aforementioned definitions of Business Education is that it is a vocational programme. This means, it is employment oriented. The employment could be for oneself or working for another person, government, agency, Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) among others.

Business education provides the knowledge, skills, attitudes and understanding needed to perform in the business world as a producer and / or consumer of goods and services that business offers (Christopher, 2013). Musa (2020:5) noted that Business Education has the following roles; to:

- Provide business teachers with the necessary competencies in both business and professional education.
- Provide competent graduates in business subjects who will be able to teach all the business subjects in the junior secondary schools and all the secretarial and accounting subjects in senior secondary schools.

The National Universities Commission (2022:166), however, gave the general objectives of Business Education as to:

- Provide opportunity for practical job preparation or vocational studies in order to make students render effective and efficient services in office, distributive and service occupations.
- Prepare students, based on interest and aptitudes needed to enter into a business occupation, advance and profit in it.
- Provide opportunities for students to develop an understanding of business and economic system of the nation so as to enable them participate actively as producers and consumers of goods and services.
- Develop in students the basic awareness of the contributions which business and office employees make to the nations' economy.
- . Develop and improve personal qualities and attitude of students as required in personal and employment situations.

There are specialty areas in Business Education. These include: Accounting Education, Entrepreneurship Education Marketing Education and Office technology management (OTM) Education.

Accounting Education train its recipients on the management of organizational financial affairs for a better informed decision making;

Entrepreneurship Education this prepares its recipients with the skill and knowledge needed for effective management of business enterprise;

Marketing Education prepares its recipients with the knowledge and skill in the presentation and distribution of products to the consumers for the satisfaction of their wants and needs and **Office Technology and Management (OTM) Education** trained their recipients with skill necessary needed to manage office matters.

The focus of this study is on the Accounting Education option. Accounting is the systematic process of keeping records of all business transactions in order to obtain information that aid in ascertaining the position of the business and in making effective business decisions. The Committee on Accounting Terminology of the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (CATAICPA) in Mae (2021) defined accounting as the art of recording, classifying and summarizing in a significant manner and in terms of money, transactions and events which are in part at least of a financial character and interpreting the results thereof. The definition contains four important elements: recording, classifying, summarizing and interpreting transactions. Similarly, The American Accounting Association (AAA) in Mae (2021) defined Accounting based on four elements: identifying, measuring communicating and decision making. Based on these elements, AAA defined Accounting as the process of identifying, measuring and communicating economic information to permit informed judgments and decision by users of the information. In this study, Accounting is defined as the process of identifying, recording, classifying, summarizing, analysing, interpreting and

presenting transactions of monetary value, to provide information about the position of the business and to make informed decision about the business.

Teaching is the process in which accounting knowledge, skills and experiences are inculcated in the learners. It is the art of helping learners to gain knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that will help them become relevant to themselves and to the society they live in. In the assertion of Sequeira (2018), teaching is a set of events, outside the learners which are designed to support internal process of learning. For Amidon in Rajagopalan (2019), teaching is an interactive process, primarily involving classroom talk which takes place between teacher and pupil and occurs during certain definable activities. Teaching could be seen as activities purposefully carried out by the teacher in a learning environment in order to create awareness and change the behaviour of the learners positively.

Rajagopalan (2019:6) gave some characteristics of teaching to include the following:

- ❖ Teaching is an effective interaction between teacher and students.
- ❖ Teaching is both arts as well as science. Teaching is an art as it calls for the exercise of talent and creativity. Teaching as science involves a repertoire of techniques, procedures and skills that can be systematically studied, described and improved. A good teacher is one who adds creativity and inspiration to the basic repertoire.
- ❖ Teaching has various forms, like formal and informal training, conditioning or indoctrination, etc.
- ❖ Teaching is dominated by the skill of communication.
- ❖ Teaching is a triple process; the three poles are, educational objectives, learning experiences and change in behaviour

Good teaching is democratic, teachers should respect their students, encourage them to ask questions, answer questions and discuss subject matter that has been introduced objectively especially in this 21st century to support the teaching of accounting courses. Notably, the Accounting Software technology. A software of this nature (QuickBook, Acumatica, Microsoft Dynamics 365's, Zohobook, FreshBook, Oracle etc) consists of programmes designed to make accounting users more productive and/or assist with personal tasks. According to Barron's Accounting Dictionary in Marushchak (2021), accounting software are programs used to maintain books of account on computers. In the assertion of Oracle (2022) accounting software manages and records the day-to-day financial transactions of an organization, including fixed asset management, expense management, revenue management, accounts receivable, accounts payable, sub-ledger accounting, and reporting and analytics. It is a computer programme that helps to manage a business by recording and processing accounting transactions with functional modules such as accounts payable, accounts receivable, payroll and trial balance.

Accounting software keeps track of an organization's assets, liabilities, revenues, and expenses. It also makes accounting computations easier to perform, understand, and analyse. In the opinion of Marushchak et al (2021), accounting software provides companies' owners and managers with quick and easy reports for decision making; it can have effect on all spheres of activity and has positive influence on companies' performance. More so, they are affordable, time savings, higher accuracy and one place for all financial tasks; they are all available to each form of business.

There are many types of accounting software used today in different business organizations. However, the adoption of accounting software depends on the needs and the type of industry. Accounting software has been categorized differently by various authors. For instance, Accounting Tools (2023) categorized the major types of accounting software into spreadsheet, commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) software, enterprise resource planning, and custom accounting software. On his part, Lalush (2023) categorized accounting software into General Accounting Software (GAS), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software, payroll software, inventory management software and invoicing software. Most software in the former category are contained in the later; thus, the later category is broader in scope and it is given attention in the study. Lalush went on to give example of the best software in each case as follows: QuickBook, Acumatica, Microsoft Dynamics 365's, ZohoBooks and FreshBooks.

QuickBook is one of the most popular accounting software programs available today that is performing most core accounting operations like general ledger, account receivable, account payable and Cash Book functions. Ask Media Group (2023) noted that it is used by small businesses, freelancers, and entrepreneurs to manage their finances; organize finances; create reports and analyse

data. QuickBook stands out as one of the best software for general accounting functions (Lalush, 2023). It is user friendly and easy to use.

The relevance of accounting software particularly the aforementioned in teaching and learning cannot be over emphasized. Accounting software in general has helped in the shift from conventional educational process to a more innovative approach to teaching and learning accounting courses. Nori, Kassim, Ahmad and Nasir (2016) remarked that such a shift allows the relevant and contemporary knowledge and skills to be spread and developed holistically in an attempt to produce accounting graduates who are equipped with the required competencies to fulfill the demands of the ever-changing business environment. Nori et al (2016) further stressed on the favourable impact that can be provided to students rather than only focusing on traditional approaches. In their terms, the employment of accounting software motivates the students to play an active role that can assist them to better understand the subject matter by simply doing what they are expected to be doing in the real world. Accounting software could deepen learning and accelerate knowledge transfer by allowing students to comfortably apply the accounting knowledge acquired in the class with what is obtainable in work environment.

How utilization of accounting software influence the teaching of accounting courses is of great concern, particularly in this study. Koko and Ajinwo (2022), perceived accounting software to have a low extent utilization by lecturers in teaching of accounting courses in tertiary institutions. The consequence is that, there would be a negative influence on the students in using accounting software they were not trained on in work environment. As Habashi (2021) clearly puts it, the lack of exposure to the computerized accounting systems in the traditional method of training, however, has made it difficult for students to transit from the college environment, which is generally just theoretical concept, to the job environment, which heavily relies on accounting software.

The moderator variable considered in the study is gender. Gender is a term used to describe the attributes in which men and women are categorized by society. The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2012) considered gender as the social attributes and opportunities associated with being male and female. The categorization makes society believe that the way the males and females perceive things seems to be different. The position of the society would be verified by findings of the study.

Gender issues are of global contemporary concern and gender disparities have been found in teachers' achievement in computer-based accounting teaching. Hassan, Hsbollah and Ali (2021) found that gender moderates the relationship between ease of use and accounting software intention and that students' behavioural intention to use accounting software was stronger for females than males. This suggest that females tend to utilize accounting software than males. This finding like the aforementioned present a notion of digital inequality between males and female. Male are better as in the first argument and female better in the second case.

Abdullahi and Mohammed (2022) revealed that male science teachers had not differ from female science teachers in the perceptions of the impact of Microsoft products on teaching and learning of science in FCT secondary schools. Similarly Chandrapala and Thevaruban (2019) found that there was no significant gender difference in the impact of accounting software utilization on students' performance in University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka. According to (Azar and Sengulec, 2011), (Bot, & Emefo, 2014) male teachers teach better than the females teachers. Others researchers opined that female teacher teaches better than male teachers (Nsofor, & Ahmed, 2014), (Adeniran, 2014). Kathy, (2011) observed that both male and female teachers teach equally. This is an indication that the existing accounts fail to resolve the contradiction between male and female achievement.

Statement of the Problem

Teaching accounting courses in most tertiary institutions is heavily dependent on the conventional approach. When the accounting graduates get to the work place the conventional manual approach of keeping records is often replaced by automated system, and they become confused. Again, monetary transactions among stakeholders in commerce and industry has become more complex than the traditional approach can handle. As a result, many companies have shifted to the use of accounting software technology. These technologies have completely changed the way professionals conduct accounting affairs, in recent times, accounting software has become an effective tool in managing business processes. Accounting software has become an integral part of all types of business.

Unfortunately, most accounting graduates experience problems using accounting software in work environment. there has been an outcry in the world of work that the graduates of accounting are lacking the competency needed in the use of accounting software and this cost businesses organizations a lot of money and time on retraining programmes for them. The authors noted further that most of the observation gathered from commerce and industry is that the accounting graduates lack the skills and knowledge that are expected of them especially in the use of accounting software due to the fact that they were not taught when they were still in school..

Given the dynamic nature of business activities and the likelihood of unique situations, it is becoming more and more important for accounting software to be integrated in the school system for teaching of accounting courses that would help develop the competitive skills for accounting graduates to succeed in work place.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the influence of the utilization of accounting software on the teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The influence of the utilization of QuickBooks on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would be of great benefit to students, teachers, schools, employers and future researchers.

The findings will equip students with relevant technical skills and knowledge that are market oriented. It will enable students to understand the digital transformations in the world of accounting and keep updated with the latest advancements to gain a competitive advantage over other candidates through job creation. Also, it will help them to improve their problem-solving skills, technical skills, and analytical thinking skills in the field of commerce and industry and other place accounting software are adopted.

The findings will help teachers of accounting courses to inculcate knowledge with ease, using the right technology to perform in their duty. It will also improve and keep them up to data with latest accounting software.

The findings of the study will help institutions teaching accounting courses with the knowledge of accounting software to increase the number of students looking to study in these colleges because these schools provide a high quality of curriculum that will improve and enhance the technical skills and knowledge which is necessary for their career.

The schools will be able to bridge the gap between the practical skills demanded by commerce and industry, and existing qualifications and competence level by accounting graduates. Institutions teaching accounting courses with the latest technology will gain an importance position in the market over their competitors among others.

The findings of the study will have significant impact on Employers. It will help them minimize their cost interns of money and time that is wasted through induction and training sessions for employees lacking requisite competencies in working with accounting software. Employing competent employees will enhance quality service delivery to their customers and increase their loyalty and expand market share. Having employees with good skills in using different software application will help the employers to maintain their position in the competitive market. Finally, the findings of the study will serve as a good source of data for future research works in this area. **Scope of the Study**

The scope of the study is tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The content scope of the study is centered on the influence of accounting software (QuickBooks) on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education (Auditing, Taxation, Financial Accounting and Cost and Management accounting) in business education department. The subject scope is limited to Business Educators in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. gender of the Business Educators served as moderator variable for the study.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of the utilization of Quick Books on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State?

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference in the mean rating on the influence of the utilization of QuickBooks on the teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions based on gender

Influence of QuickBooks on the Teaching of Accounting Courses

The introduction of technology in the field of accounting has revolutionized the way accounting courses are taught. One such technological tool that has had a significant impact is QuickBooks. Intuit QuickBooks is a popular accounting software developed by cott Cook and Tom Proulx in the year 1983 . According to Intuit (2022) QuickBooks is a user-friendly, simple accounting software that tracks business income and expenses, and organises financial information. It is designed to help small and medium-sized businesses manage their financial transactions, track expenses, create invoices, and generate financial reports.

QuickBooks is widely used by businesses to streamline their accounting processes and make informed financial decisions. Consumer Research Institute (2023) reported that QuickBooks is one of the most popular accounting software programs available, and it offers a wide range of features that make it an ideal choice for businesses. It offers various features such as payroll management, inventory tracking, and tax preparation. The Ask Media Group (2022) elucidated that QuickBooks has features that enable business organization to create recurring payments, create checks and print them, track mileage, invoice customers, manage contractors, pay employees, monitor inventory, prepare tax returns and much more.

QuickBooks software has in the Icon bar special functions that makes accounting job easy. Meru Accounting (2022) elucidated that there are five basic functions of QuickBooks software. There are categorized into Vendors, Customers, Employees, Company, and Banking. Vendors automates the function associated with accounts payables. It enables users to enter bills and use the pay bill function to initiate online payment along with the Vendor center. It also allows one to make purchase orders, record inventory, and enter bills to schedule supplier payments. It helps also to track upcoming payments.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive survey research design. According to Gauri, 2025, descriptive design is a type of research design that utilizes both quantitative and qualitative methods of research to collect data to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. Descriptive research is a methodological approach that seeks to depict the characteristics of a phenomenon or subject under investigation. In scientific inquiry, it serves as a foundational tool for researchers aiming to observe, record, and analyze the intricate details of a particular topic (Sunaina, 2023).

The research work was conducted in Cross River State. The area of the study was tertiary institutions offering Business Education in Cross River State. The content area of the study is centred on the influence of the utilization of accounting software on the teaching of accounting courses in Business Education. 21st century is technological era in which traditional method of teaching accounting failed to produce effective and productive work force for the industries after graduation. The subject scope is delimited to Business Educators in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. Gender of the Business Educators served as moderators for the study. The population for this study consisted of 106 Business educators of the tertiary institutions that offer Business Education in Cross River State. The population is made up business educators from the following tertiary institutions: University of Calabar, Cross River State University. The whole (106) lecturers of the institutions that offer accounting courses in Business Education in their schools participated in the study. There was no sampling since the population is manageable. Thus the entire population of 106 Business Educators was used for the study. The instrument that the researcher used for data collection is a structured questionnaire. A four-point rating scale was used to measure Business Educators opinion on the influence of the utilization of accounting software on the teaching of accounting courses in business education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The respondents were to select from the options of Strongly agree (SA = 4) , Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) The instrument is also made up of 60 items; 10 question items for each research questions. To determine reliability of the instrument, the researcher produced 30 copies of the instrument where it was trial tested on the business educators at College of Education Katsina Ala, Benue State. The structured questionnaire was passed for reliability using Crombach alpha reliability. The entire instrument has

10 question items. The instrument was assessed for reliability which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77. The method used by the researcher to collect data for the study, the researcher visited the institutions concerned and administered 106 questionnaire to the respondents with the assistance of a staff from the department of the institution. All the 106 copies of the questionnaire were collected back intact. Data collected for this study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, the mean was used to determine the level of responses while the standard deviation was used to determine the extent to which the respondents' responses cluster or deviate from the means. The mean is interpreted based on the four scale points used on the instrument SA = 4 (3.5 – 4.00), A = 3 (2.5 – 3.00), D = 2 (1.5 – 2.49) and SD = 1 (0 – 1.49). Similarly, t-test was used to test the research hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance comparing the value of p. value against the 0.05 level of significant. When the value the t-test conducted shows that p.value < 0.05 the null hypothesis be rejected vice versa. The decision rule in this study is that any outcome that yielded a mean that is less than 2.50 is that, the software is considered to have negative influence on its utilization on the effective teaching of accounting courses in business education while an outcome that yielded a mean of 2.50 to 4.00 is considered to have positive influence on its utilization on the effective teaching of accounting courses in business education. To accept any hypotheses, the the level of significant (0.05) must be less than p. value otherwise the null hypotheses be rejected.

RESULTS

Data collected for the study are presented below:

Research Question 1: *What is the Influence of the utilization of QuickBooks on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Cross River State?*

Summary of data analysis is presented on Table 1.

Table Mean responses on the Influence of the utilization of QuickBooks on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Cross River State

SN	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	QuickBooks software provides accounting teachers with information for the development of accounting course contents for effective teaching of accounting courses	4.00	0.00	PI
2	QuickBooks provides teacher with information needed for effective teaching of accounting	3.82	0.39	PI
3	QuickBooks facilitates effective online teaching of accounting courses	3.79	0.41	PI
4	QuickBooks serve as a reference material for effective teaching accounting courses	3.48	0.50	PI
5	It creates and print documents needed for effective teaching of accounting source of business documents	3.41	0.49	PI
6	QuickBooks enhances teachers with problem-solving skills, preparing students for the collaborative nature of the accounting profession	3.51	0.50	PI
7	QuickBooks provide platform for teachers to master skills that are needed for effective teaching of accounting courses	3.56	0.50	PI
8	QuickBooks provides an interactive platform for effective teaching accounting principles and concepts	3.73	0.44	PI
9	QuickBooks helps to reinforce teachers understanding of theoretical concepts through practical application for the effective teaching of accounting	3.78	0.41	PI
10	QuickBooks offers a user-friendly interface that simplifies complex accounting tasks for effective teaching of accounting courses.	3.71	0.46	PI

Source: Field work 2025; PI = Positive influence

The result of the analysis of all the variables reveals that QuickBooks software provides accounting teachers with information for the development of accounting course contents for effective teaching of accounting courses (Mean 4.00, SD 0.00), QuickBooks provides teacher with information needed for effective teaching of accounting (mean 3.82 SD 0.39), QuickBooks helps to reinforce teachers understanding of theoretical concepts through practical application for the effective teaching of accounting (mean 3.78 SD 0.41 etc), Base on the decision rule in this study that any outcome that yielded a mean of 2.5 and above be considered to have positive influence on its utilization, This

means that the utilization of QuickBooks Accounting software has positive influence on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Cross River State
HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating on the Influence of the utilization of Quick books on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State

Data collected with the instrument were separated for males and females and used to test this hypothesis using t-test of difference between independent samples. Summary of data analysis is presented on Table 7.

Table : t-test of difference in the mean responses of male and females on Influence of the utilization of Quick books on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education

S/N	Variables	Gender				t-value	p-value
		M (n = 52)		F (n = 54)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	0000 SD		
1.	QuickBooks software provides accounting teachers with information for the development of accounting course contents for effective teaching of accounting courses	4.00	0.00	4.00	0.00	-	-
2.	QuickBooks provides teacher with information needed for effective teaching of accounting	3.83	0.38	3.81	0.39	0.16	0.872
3.	QuickBooks facilitates effective online teaching of accounting courses	3.73	0.45	3.85	0.36	1.54	0.127
4.	QuickBooks serve as a reference material for effective teaching accounting courses	3.42	0.49	3.54	0.50	1.17	0.245
5.	It creates and print documents needed for effective teaching of accounting source of business documents	3.38	0.49	3.43	0.49	0.43	0.669
6.	QuickBooks enhances teachers with problem-solving skills, preparing students for the collaborative nature of the accounting profession	3.44	0.50	3.57	0.49	1.36	0.178
7.	QuickBooks provide platform for teachers to master skills that are needed for effective teaching of accounting courses	3.65	0.48	3.46	0.50	2.00	0.049
8.	QuickBooks provides an interactive platform for effective teaching accounting principles and concepts	3.83	0.38	3.65	0.48	2.11	0.037
9.	QuickBooks helps to reinforce teachers understanding of theoretical concepts through practical application for the effective teaching of accounting	3.79	0.41	3.78	0.42	0.13	0.895
10.	QuickBooks offers a user-friendly interface that simplifies complex accounting tasks for effective teaching of accounting courses.	3.71	0.46	3.70	0.46	0.09	0.930

* Significant at $p < 0.05$

The result of the hypothesis test conducted, several variables indicated that utilization of QuickBooks helps to reinforce teachers understanding of theoretical concepts through practical application for the effective teaching of accounting, quickbook accounting software quickbooks provides teacher with information needed for effective teaching of accounting (0.930, 0.872 and others meaning to say that utilization of accounting software has a positive influence on the effective teaching of accounting courses however few variables indicated that the utilization of the software is significant meaning to say that the software has a negative influence on the effective teaching of accounting courses in business education.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data presented and analysed, the below findings were made:

There are ten (10) items under the influence of QuickBooks, eight items strongly agree while two agree that QuickBooks influence effective teaching of accounting courses in business education. From the finding QuickBooks influence effective teaching of accounting courses in Business education in Tertiary institutions in Cross River State. The institutions are to develop the software in their various to serve its purpose. The findings in Table 1 revealed that utilization of QuickBooks influences effective teaching of Accounting courses in Business Education. In Table 1 the result yielded a grand mean of 3.68 with standard deviation of 0.41 where the hypothesis in Table 7 revealed the t_{crt} is greater than t_{cal} ($t_{\text{crt}} 1.96 > t_{\text{cal}} 0.88$ at alpha level of 0.05. Following the decision rule, since the t_{crt} is greater than t_{cal} , the null hypothesis upholds that there is significant influence of the utilization of Quick book on the effective teaching of accounting courses'. QuickBooks provides educators with the needed information for the development of accounting course content, facilitate effective teaching, provision of platform for mastery of skills needed as well as provision of reference materials for effective teaching of accounting courses in business education.

There was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female on the influence of the utilization of QuickBook on the effective teaching of accounting courses in Business Education in tertiary institutions in Cross River State. However there are two items which indicates that there are significant difference while eight items indicated that there are no significant difference.

CONCLUSION

The place of technology in this 21st century cannot be over emphasised, technology has come to help man in all aspect of life. The emergence of technology has replaced the traditional way of teaching accounting. Teaching accounting courses through the utilization of accounting software provide accounting graduates with the skill, knowledge and competent for effective performance needed by the industries that they are going to serve after graduation. It is on these bases that the researcher conducted a study to determine the influence of the utilization of accounting software on the effective teaching of accounting courses in business education. It was established that the utilization of accounting software enhances effective teaching of accounting courses there by making teaching and learning more relevant capable of meeting up the requirements of the industries at work place, This study help in the area of collaboration among students in the area of knowledge and skill in the utilization of accounting software, Tertiary institutions and Business organizations as well in the provision of the facilities need to develop the software in various institutions of learning. The study also recognised the importance of gender, male and female computes in the world pf work in this present 21st century as they are exposed to the use of accounting software during their studies. Education stakeholders, curriculum developers and institutions should make deliberate effort to include accounting software in accounting programmes of study, develop the software in institutions that teaches accounting courses for effective teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1 Tertiary institutions should develop accounting software in their schools for the purpose of practical teaching of accounting courses
- 2 Curriculum developers should include accounting software in the tertiary institutions curriculum
- 3 There should be workshop and seminar on the utilization of accounting software for accounting teachers.
- 4 Text books should be published on the utilization of accounting software

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